

Sci!lake

Scientific Lake

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Abstract

In this deliverable report, we describe the beta release of a smart knowledge discovery service, which has been developed in the context of the SciLake project and leverages SciLake's Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs) and the various technologies provided by the Scientific Lake tier of SciLake's architecture. The service is designed to leverage the contents of the Scientific Lake to calculate indicators of scientific impact for research products and offer, based on them, useful functionalities to researchers so that they are able to (a) prioritise their reading of the relevant literature when searching for a specific subject of interest (b) uncover latent knowledge that could be instrumental in accelerating their research conclusions, and (c) identify emerging trends related to research topics of interest. The report provides references to the respective open code bases and elaborates on the technical details related to the development of the various components.

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Author List

ORGANISATION	NAME	CONTACT INFORMATION
ATHENA RC	Thanasis Vergoulis	vergoulis@athenarc.gr
ATHENA RC	Serafeim Chatzopoulos	schatz@athenarc.gr
ATHENA RC	Sotiris Kotitsas	sotiris.kotitsas@athenarc.gr

Contributor List

ORGANISATION	NAME	CONTACT INFORMATION
CNR	Miriam Baglioni	miriam.baglioni@isti.cnr.it
SIRIS	César Parra Rojas	cesar.parra@sirisacademic.com

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Abbreviation List

- **AI:** Artificial Intelligence
- **API:** Application Programming Interface
- **DOI:** Digital Object Identifier
- **FORD:** Fields Of Research and Development
- **FoS:** Fields of Science
- **HF:** Hugging Face
- **KG:** Knowledge Graph
- **LDA:** Latent Dirichlet Allocation (topic modeling algorithm)
- **LLMs:** Large Language Models
- **NC:** Nominal Chunk
- **POS:** Part of speech
- **SDGs:** Sustainable Development Goals
- **SKG:** Scientific Knowledge Graph
- **UI:** User Interface
- **URL:** Uniform Resource Locator

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1. Executive Summary

In today's fast-paced world of scientific research, the sheer volume of available research outputs, such as publications, datasets, and software, has a dual impact on researchers. On one hand, the abundance of valuable information provides a rich foundation for their work. On the other hand, navigating this vast knowledge space can be overwhelming, particularly given the varying quality of research works available. Contrary to the past, today's researchers face the challenge not of a lack of information, but of efficiently discovering relevant and high-quality knowledge.

Building services that facilitate scientific knowledge discovery is crucial for accelerating research, innovation, and progress. By providing researchers with advanced tools to seamlessly search, filter, and access the research products that are most valuable and relevant to their research, we can empower them to spend more time on actual research activities and less on navigating through information overload. Finally, as a side effect, such services can democratise access to information, ensuring that researchers from diverse backgrounds have equal opportunities to benefit from the collective pool of scientific knowledge.

The concept of the Scientific Lake, which is being introduced by the SciLake project, offers a foundation of cutting-edge technologies that can significantly simplify the development of added-value services aiming to facilitate scientific knowledge discovery. At the core of this concept are Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs), which provide an efficient means of organising, querying, and accessing both domain-agnostic and domain-specific knowledge. This facilitates the uncovering of hidden connections between research-related entities and highlights emerging trends, making them invaluable tools for advancing scientific discovery and enabling informed decisions for the work of researchers.

In this report, we describe the final release of a smart knowledge discovery service, which has been developed in the context of the SciLake project and leverages SciLake's SKGs and the various technologies provided by the Scientific Lake tier of SciLake's architecture. The service is designed to leverage the contents of the Scientific Lake to calculate indicators of scientific impact for research products and offer, based on them, useful functionalities to researchers so that they are able to (a) prioritise their reading of the relevant literature when searching for a specific subject of interest (b) uncover latent knowledge that could be instrumental in accelerating their research conclusions, and (c) identify emerging trends related to research topics of interest. The service is also modular and configurable so that it can be tailored to the needs and the specificities of different scientific domains. In the context of the project, different instances of the service components are configured based on the domains of the

project pilots: Cancer research, Neuroscience, Energy, and Transport (Maritime and CCAM). These instances are used to demonstrate the service and evaluate its value, as well the value of the underlying Scientific Lake.

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2. Introduction

In recent years, the volume of scientific and research output has surged dramatically. This explosion in scientific content is driven by several factors, including the increasing number of researchers entering various fields [1] and the pervasive "publish or perish" culture that pressures academics to continually produce and publish new research. Additionally, rapid advances in Artificial Intelligence (AI) have enabled the widespread adoption of AI-assisted tools for literature analysis, data processing, and manuscript preparation, further accelerating the growth of scientific output.

On one hand, this proliferation of research is beneficial for researchers as it results in a vast volume of knowledge that they can draw upon to advance their own studies. The extensive range of available content fosters research, innovation, cross-disciplinary discoveries, and rapid advancements in science and technology. However, this rapid increase in research output also presents significant challenges. The sheer volume of published work makes it increasingly difficult for researchers to identify valuable and relevant studies within this overload of information. Various studies and reports [2] have highlighted that the accelerated pace of research production can lead to a decline in quality of published works. Consequently, it becomes more challenging for researchers to discern high-quality information, potentially hindering scientific progress. This dual-edged nature of the burgeoning research landscape underscores the need for advanced tools and services that can help researchers efficiently navigate vast amounts of data to find the most pertinent and high-quality information.

To make matters worse, current scientific knowledge discovery services tend to focus predominantly on publications, neglecting the diverse and heterogeneous nature of modern research output. It is increasingly recognized that valuable research contributions come in many forms beyond traditional papers, including research data, software, peer reviews, and more. This narrow focus on publications creates significant challenges for researchers who need comprehensive access to all relevant resources to advance their work. Addressing this issue is crucial because each type of research output provides unique insights and plays a vital role in the scientific process. Indicatively, research data can offer detailed experimental results and raw information that underpins published findings, while software tools and algorithms developed during research projects are essential for replicating studies and building upon previous work. Therefore, developing knowledge discovery services that encompass a wider array of resources is essential for fostering a more holistic and effective research environment. By doing so, we can ensure that researchers have access to a complete spectrum of scientific contributions, facilitating better-informed decisions, fostering innovation, and ultimately advancing the frontiers of knowledge more efficiently.

In our opinion, the Scientific Lake concept introduced by the SciLake project holds significant potential for paving the way to address these challenges. As detailed in deliverables D2.1¹ (“Initial version of the Scientific Lake Service”) and D2.2² (“Final version of the Scientific Lake Service”), this concept offers a suite of valuable components that enable domain experts to better extract and organise domain-specific knowledge, facilitating the development of added-value services for scientific discovery. At the core of this concept are various Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs), which provide efficient and effective ways to query and explore the encoded knowledge, helping service developers in revealing valuable insights.

Given the importance of knowledge discovery activities for science, the aforementioned challenges, and the potential of the Scientific Lake concept to help address them, we have chosen to implement a smart knowledge discovery service on top of the Scientific Lake that we are building in the context of the project. By leveraging the comprehensive capabilities of SKGs, this service can significantly enhance the ability of researchers to navigate the vast and diverse landscape of scientific outputs in their scientific domains of interest. The SciLake project's approach ensures that the diverse nature of research contributions, including datasets and research software, is integrated and accessible, thus providing a more holistic and enriched platform for scientific discovery.

In the following sections, we provide a comprehensive overview of the SciLake smart knowledge discovery service. Section 3 outlines the design process followed for the service. In Section 4, we offer implementation details for all the major components of the service together with references to the respective code bases, and in Section 5, we present use cases that demonstrate its value. Finally, Section 6, summarises the report and briefly discusses the next steps in further developing the service.

¹ SciLake D2.1: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12799952>

² SciLake D2.2: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18243604>

3. Design

In this section, we quickly discuss the main requirements of the service, the process followed during its design, and how it is integrated into the SciLake ecosystem. More details about the design process can be found in Deliverable D1.2 (“Initial integrated system”). It is also worth noting that this section is a slightly updated version of the respective section of Deliverable D3.1³ (“Initial version of the smart impact-driven discovery service”).

3.1. Main requirements

Our aim for SciLake’s smart knowledge discovery service is to provide researchers with a powerful tool to navigate the vast knowledge space of their domain while also offering valuable insights for their research activities.

More specifically, the service should be able to support the following main functionalities:

- Offer advanced search functionalities for research products and domain-specific entities, providing multiple ways of presenting, filtering, and ordering the search results.
- Offer integration with domain-specific SKGs, exploiting their contents to present the search results together with valuable enrichments coming from the underlying SKGs in an intuitive and insightful way.
- Calculate advanced citation-based impact indicators for research products and leverage them in (a) ordering, filtering, and/or organising the search results to facilitate the identification of valuable research products and new knowledge discovery; (b) providing analytics and visualisations that can help in identifying and monitoring trends in scientific topics and their evolution.
- Implement impact propagation and aggregation techniques to calculate enhanced citation-based indicators for various types of research products beyond publications, such as datasets, as well as for related domain-specific entities, investigating also the enhancement of citation links with other types of acknowledgement links between research products (e.g., in-text mentions) or semantics (e.g., leveraging citation intent classification).
- Calculate classifications of research products in scientific fields and domains based on their metadata and contents and use these classifications to (a) provide useful enrichments for the search results, (b) provide insights about the level of impact of research products into particular scientific fields/domains, and (c) give valuable input

³ SciLake D3.1: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12806146>

to the components providing analytics and visualisations for topic trends and evolution.

- Leverage contemporary AI or machine learning techniques to produce summaries of the search results.

Based on the previous requirements, the service is expected to have the following distinct components to support the aforementioned functionalities:

- Field-extraction component
- Citation-based impact analysis component
- Topic analysis component
- Knowledge discovery portal

In addition, recognizing that each scientific domain has unique requirements for knowledge discovery, encompassing, for instance, distinct domain entities and research methodologies, it became evident that we should design the service with adaptability in mind. It was crucial to ensure that the service could be tailored to accommodate the diverse needs of each pilot domain effectively. As such, the service should be configurable to meet the following requirements:

- The service should support multiple ways to order search results and should be possible for service instance administrators to configure which are the ordering options provided to the end-user for their particular instance as well as which is the default option for results ordering for the instance.
- The service should be configurable by service instance administrators regarding the type of research products and/or domain entities that will be presented to the end-user during the knowledge discovery process.
- The service should be able to present a particular selection of enrichments for the search results based on the SKGs connected to the particular service instance and this selection should be configurable by the service instance administrators.
- The service should accommodate feedback from domain experts regarding improvements or additions to the metadata kept for the underlying SKGs towards a better representation of the respective domain (e.g., fixing terminology based on well-established vocabularies or taxonomies). These changes could be part of an initial configuration process for the development of the SKGs that happens offline before the creation of the service instance. Small adaptations of the SKG content should be possible afterwards, as well.

Finally, considering that this service will be evaluated by the SciLake pilot representatives and that it provides a user-friendly interface through which other SciLake components can also be

assessed⁴ (e.g., the outputs of SKG enrichments produced by the field extraction component or by similar components developed within this or other work packages), we have added the extra requirement for the service to include basic feedback mechanisms to support this kind of evaluation activities.

Having determined the aforementioned main requirements, we have then selected an appropriate design approach.

3.2. Design approach

A key objective for the project is to involve researchers closely in the design and development process even from early stages. Within the project, use-case representatives are the domain experts involved in these activities. Hence, we placed significant emphasis on presenting early prototypes to the pilot representatives (following an early and rapid prototyping approach) and gathering feedback related to their specific use cases on many occasions.

In addition, we designed a series of parallel activities to reinforce the previous process. First, we collected early feedback from pilot representatives to understand their use cases and specific needs for the service (documented in Deliverable D1.1). Then, in November 2023, we organised a hands-on workshop in Barcelona to refine these use cases, as a joint exercise between the technical partners and the pilot representatives. We have also drafted an internal document outlining a roadmap for SciLake piloting activities to enhance communication between technical partners and pilot representatives, and we formalised the collection of information about domain knowledge spaces and SKG data models using living documents.

The aforementioned approach is part of the design process followed by the project for all software development activities. More details about this process can be found in Deliverable D1.2 ("Initial integrated system").

⁴ See also SciLake Deliverable D5.1 ("Report on pilot setup and evaluation methodology"): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14748857>

3.3. Integration into SciLake ecosystem

SciLake's ultimate goal is to provide a suite of customizable components designed to facilitate the creation, interlinking, and maintenance of domain-specific, community-managed SKGs, as well as components to offer a unified method for accessing and querying the included assets. All these components can be deployed and executed across a range of machines, forming a "Scientific Lake": a federated, highly customizable computational infrastructure composed of loosely-connected nodes. Each node hosts or executes a subset of the SciLake components tailored to the needs of the respective use case. This Scientific Lake concept aims to enable and support the creation of value-added services that enhance knowledge discovery and other essential research activities.

The smart knowledge discovery service detailed in this report is built upon this foundational concept. Implemented as a value-added service that can be deployed on top of an instance of the Scientific Lake, it is also highly customizable by design to meet the specific needs of different scientific domains. This flexibility ensures that the service can adapt to the unique requirements of each domain, thereby providing a powerful tool for researchers to navigate and utilise the vast expanse of scientific knowledge effectively.

The smart knowledge discovery service has two bundles of components: the first comprises a set of tools that can calculate SKG enrichments that are valuable for the knowledge discovery process; the second provides a powerful user interface (UI) to its end users (i.e., domain experts), offering functionalities that facilitate scientific knowledge discovery. Both types of components are designed to consume the contents of the SKGs that belong to the Scientific Lake mainly via the respective (open) API calls provided by the SciLake nodes. The APIs, among others, support posing Cypher queries to the SKGs exploiting the underlying graph database technology (for details, see D2.1 and D2.2). This offers a lot of expressivity for the type of knowledge that can be retrieved from the SKGs facilitating the implementation of advanced features to serve the domain experts in the context of scientific knowledge discovery.

4. Implementation

In this section, we provide implementation details for all the major components of the service, accompanied by a comprehensive overview of the related development activities as well as links to the respective code bases and documentation websites (when applicable). The implementation was guided by the design approach presented in Section 3.2. We describe all technical activities organised by component, based on the components that have been identified during the service design phase, elaborated in Section 3.1. This organisation of the section in component-based subsections was selected to allow for easy navigation and independent reading of the technical details related to each of the components.

4.1. Field extraction component

The field extraction component is responsible for enhancing and refining a suite of classification tools designed to assign Field of Science (FoS)⁵ labels to scientific publications. This initiative aims to support the generation of advanced, field-weighted, multi-perspective impact analysis services. Building on a hierarchical classification system initially developed through two European Union studies on Open Science⁶, our approach leveraged a publication-based classifier. Such a classification system can be valuable in improving the precision and utility of scientific impact assessments across diverse research fields. In the context of the SciLake project, this classifier and the respective FoS taxonomy was adapted and expanded to better serve the needs of the SciLake's pilots. Finally, a second classifier responsible for assigning scientific publications to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)⁷ was also integrated. The SDGs provide a globally recognized framework for addressing critical socio-economic and environmental challenges. By aligning scientific publications with specific SDGs, we can facilitate a more fine-grained and actionable understanding of how research contributes to sustainable development. This view could be of particular importance for some of the SciLake pilots (e.g., the Transportation Research pilot).

⁵ A field of science (FoS) taxonomy in general is a structured classification system that organises scientific disciplines and sub-disciplines. In Section 4.1.1, we define our own structured classification system. In this deliverable we refer to it as FoS taxonomy, unless otherwise specified.

⁶ Concretely, (a) the "Study to support the monitoring and evaluation of the Framework Programme for research and innovation along Key Impact Pathways" under development, and, (b) the MOAP study entitled: "[Monitoring the open access policy of Horizon 2020](#)".

⁷ The 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), a call for action by all countries - developed and developing - in a global partnership ([SDG](#))

In the next subsections, we first discuss the FoS Taxonomy (Section 4.1.1), Classifier (4.1.2), and Taxonomy Mapper (4.1.3), which constitute key parts of SciLake's FoS component, and then we present the implementation details of the SDG Classifier (Section 4.1.4).

4.1.1. FoS Taxonomy

The Field of Science (FoS) Taxonomy is a hierarchical structure of scientific fields that is used as a classification scheme by the FoS Classifier to automatically assign scientific publications to FoS labels at various levels of detail.

More concretely, the aforementioned FoS classification scheme is underpinned by the OECD disciplines/fields of research and development (FORD) classification scheme, developed in the framework of the Frascati Manual⁸ and used to classify R&D units and resources in broad (first level - L1) and narrower (second level - L2) knowledge domains based primarily on the R&D subject matter. We extend the OECD/FORD scheme by manually linking FoS labels of the SCIENCEMETRIX⁹ classification scheme to OECD/FORD Level-2 categories, creating a hierarchical 3-layer taxonomy. To facilitate a more fine-grained analysis, we further enhance the Field-of-Science taxonomy with Level-4 (L4), Level-5 (L5) and Level-6 (L6) fields by employing a pipeline of AI techniques.

Generating Level-4 FoS fields: The intuition behind the approach is that venues (conferences or journals) under each Level 3 FoS (e.g., Energy) are creating small communities citing each other. For example, venues that are related to "Renewable Energy" will cite each other more frequently than venues under other Level 3 FoS or venues that are frequent under other subfields of Energy or "general science" venues. We removed from the process "general science" venues (e.g. PlosONE) and created a venue-to-venue citation graph specific to each Level 3 FoS. The nodes on the venue-to-venue graphs are venues and the edges stem from publications that are assigned to the respective Level 3 FoS and are published in venues that exist in the venue-to-venue graphs. We performed community detection on each Level 3 FoS venue-to-venue graph. The resulting communities in each Level 3 FoS graph are the Level 4 FoS fields.

The Level 4 FoS fields are communities of venues and we do not have a label describing each community. The following table provides an example of a Level 4 FoS community of venues.

⁸ <https://www.oecd.org/sti/inno/frascati-manual.htm>

⁹ SCIENCEMETRIX Classification provides a list of Journal Classifications with FoS categories. We get the lower level of this classification to manually link it with the OECD/FORD Level-2 categories.

Level 4 ID	Community of Venues	Manual Annotation
L4_AI_9	acl, naacl, tacl, acm trans asian low resour lang inf process, coling, computational linguistics, emnlp, ijcnlp, int joint conf artif, lang resources evaluation, nat lang eng	Natural Language Processing

Table 1: Example of a Level 4 FoS field under the domain of AI. The Level 4 FoS fields get an ID as seen in the first column. The second column presents a community of venues under a Level 4 FoS. The third column presents a possible interpretation/label of the community presented in the second column. We cannot manually assign a label to each Level 4 FoS field due to their cardinality and the required domain expertise.

To provide a label for each Level 4 FoS field, we utilised synthesis publications¹⁰ and Wikipedia. We identified synthesis publications existing under each Level 4 FoS field (e.g. "Applying Natural Language Processing and Hierarchical Machine Learning Approaches to Text Difficulty Classification" is a synthesis publication in Artificial Intelligence). For each synthesis publication we processed its title (e.g. lemmatization, stopword removal, POS tagging) and extracted Nominal Chunks (NCs)¹¹. One aspect of this approach that requires attention is that the title might also include technologies and very granular fields that would belong to lower levels of our taxonomy. We performed the same text preprocessing in the section titles of each of the synthesis publications and filtered out the common NCs. By performing agglomerative clustering on the resulting NCs and keeping the most representative ones, we end up with NCs that are well-defined and describe the Level 4 FoS field. The following table provides an example of a cluster of NCs in their respective Level 4 FoS field.

¹⁰ As synthesis publications, are considered publications with more that 100 references, which usually are literature reviews or surveys, and in general, they try to sum up a scientific field.

¹¹ Lemmatization refers to reducing words to their base or root form. Stopword removal refers to eliminating common, non-informative words from text. POS tagging refers to assigning parts of speech to each word in a sentence which indicate the grammatical function of the word within the text and Nominal Chunks (NCs) refer to identifying and extracting noun phrases from text.

Level 4 ID	Cluster of NCs	Wikipedia Assigned name
L4_AI_9	'natural language processing article', 'natural language', 'natural language processing', 'nlp', 'speech language processing', 'computational natural language processing'	Natural language processing/Computational linguistics

Table 2: Example of a cluster of NCs of a Level 4 FoS field. Some clusters have more NCs, however for readability and presentation reasons of this deliverable, we have randomly sampled, if available, 10 NCs. The automatically assigned name to this Level 4 FoS field from Wikipedia is also visible in the third column.

We searched each NC from the top-2 most representative clusters to Wikipedia science pages and kept the top-2 most common titles as the name of the Level 4 FoS field.

Generating Level-5 FoS fields: To identify the Level 5 FOS fields, we must first discover the underlying communities formed by the scientific publications within each Level 4 FoS field. Based on the premise that a scientific publication cites thematically related works, we can connect these publications by creating publication-to-publication graphs for each Level 4 FOS field, utilising their citations and references. After creating the graphs, we can again perform community detection to generate communities of publications, which now represent the Level 5 FoS fields. To identify the thematic focus of each community, we applied topic modelling¹² to the publications within each community. The most frequent topic of each community is considered to be the Level 5 FoS field. The most descriptive n-grams of the rest of the topics under each community are considered to be the Level 6 FoS fields. An example of a Level 5 FoS field (topic) along with Level 6 FoS fields is visible in Figure 1.

By employing open-source Large Language Models (LLMs) and through prompt engineering and few-shot prompting, we can generate a scientific label associated with each Level 5 FoS field (topic). In the following figure a snapshot of the complete taxonomy is presented:

¹² We utilise BERTopic for the topic model algorithm.

Figure 1: A snapshot of the Field of Science Taxonomy.

More information, results and examples regarding the construction of the FoS taxonomy are included in the relevant papers in Table 3. For the complete FoS taxonomy and LLM prompt refer to the repository link in Table 3. For an overview of Level 1 (L1) - Level 3 (L3) FoS fields refer to [OpenAIRE FoS¹³](#).

Through the lifecycle of the project and through our collaboration with OpenAIRE, we have identified some issues with the current version of the FoS Taxonomy. To evaluate and refine the overall coverage of the FoS taxonomy, we conducted a systematic alignment between the FoS taxonomy (SciNoBo) and two well-established scientific classification systems: Scopus and EuroSciVoc. This analysis aimed to identify overlaps, gaps, and structural mismatches across taxonomies, and to inform subsequent taxonomy refinement. Indicatively, it revealed a lot of alignment patterns and some inconsistencies. For example, SciNoBo's Engineering and Technology → Environmental Engineering shows a close correspondence with EuroSciVoc's Environmental Engineering, indicating good conceptual alignment. In contrast, SciNoBo's Agricultural Biotechnology → Food Science aligns more naturally with EuroSciVoc's Engineering and Technology → Food Technology, suggesting that food-related disciplines span multiple high-level domains and may require clearer modelling of cross-domain relationships. Similarly, comparisons with Scopus highlighted differences in granularity:

¹³ By typing in the search bar, a user can also browse the L4 FoS fields.

SciNoBo's Animal and Dairy Science → Dairy & Animal Science aligns with Scopus's broader Agricultural and Biological Sciences category, indicating that SciNoBo provides finer-grained distinctions that are not always explicitly represented in Scopus. Due to the size constraints of this deliverable, it is not feasible to include the full set of comparison tables here. The complete Scopus and EuroSciVoc comparison results are therefore provided as supplementary material and can be accessed at: [SciNoBo FoS Taxonomy and Scopus alignment](#) and [SciNoBo FoS Taxonomy and EurosciVoc alignment](#).

Based on expert curation and insights gained from the alignment with Scopus and EuroSciVoc, a revised version of the taxonomy (SciNoBo Taxonomy V2) was produced. During this revision process, several recurring structural and conceptual issues were identified. These issues were categorised into four main cases, each representing a distinct class of taxonomy design problem, along with targeted solutions.

The first case concerns **Parent Nodes with Only One Child Node**. Such structures indicate limited conceptual branching and add unnecessary hierarchy without increasing semantic clarity. For example, in the earlier taxonomy version, a parent node such as Materials Science contained a single child node Advanced Materials, offering no meaningful subdivision. In SciNoBo Taxonomy V2, such cases were resolved either by collapsing the hierarchy (removing the redundant parent) or by introducing additional, well-defined sibling subfields where justified, informed by external taxonomies.

The second case addresses **Nodes with Child Nodes Sharing the Same Name as the Parent**. This redundancy can cause confusion, as it is unclear whether the child node represents a specialisation or merely duplicates the parent concept. An illustrative example is a structure where Environmental Engineering appears as both a parent node and a child node under itself. In the revised taxonomy, these cases were resolved by replacing the duplicated child with more specific subfields (e.g., Carbon Capture Engineering, Natural Resources Management) or by restructuring the hierarchy to eliminate unnecessary repetition.

The third case focuses on **Different Nodes with Child Nodes Sharing the Same Name**. In these situations, identical child nodes appear under multiple parents, leading to ambiguity and inconsistent navigation. For instance, a node such as Environmental Engineering appeared under both Environmental engineering and Environmental biotechnology in the previous version. In SciNoBo Taxonomy V2, such duplicates were reviewed and consolidated by assigning the concept to the most semantically appropriate parent, while removing or renaming redundant occurrences elsewhere.

The fourth case examines situations where the **Taxonomy Stops at Level 2**, resulting in overly coarse classifications that are insufficient for detailed field extraction and pilot use cases. For example, a high-level category such as Medical and health sciences → Medical

biotechnology had no further subdivisions, despite the existence of subfields such as Tissue Engineering and Genetic Engineering. To address this, the revised taxonomy extends these branches to deeper levels, drawing from EuroSciVoc and Scopus to ensure both completeness and alignment with common scientific practice.

Given the number of changes introduced in SciNoBo Taxonomy V2—including node additions, removals, renamings, and reassignments—this section provides only a high-level overview of the identified issue types and the corresponding solutions. The complete list of revisions are documented in the SciNoBo Taxonomy V2 report, available at: [SciNoBo Taxonomy V2](#).

Finally, our Field of Science taxonomy is explicitly cited in Salatino et al.'s [16] comprehensive survey of knowledge organization systems as the OpenAIRE Field of Science Taxonomy and is analysed alongside other major multifield classification schemes. The study positions our taxonomy as one of the few multifield Knowledge organization systems (KOSs) that achieves broad disciplinary coverage across all major research areas, as illustrated in the coverage heatmap (Figure 2), where it is shown to consistently represent most domains beyond mere high-level mentions. Furthermore, the comparative assessment in Figure 3 highlights the taxonomy as a balanced solution in terms of comprehensiveness, depth, update frequency, and openness, distinguishing it from several alternative systems that either lack sufficient granularity, are infrequently maintained, or impose restrictive licensing conditions. The inclusion of our Field of Science Taxonomy among the most relevant multifield KOSs in this survey confirms its role as a mature, open, and infrastructure-ready component of the Open Science ecosystem, suitable for large-scale scholarly indexing.

Figure 2: Figure from Salatino et al. [16]. Coverage of the multifield KOSs. In green the main fields, in blue the minor ones, only partially represented, and in orange the fields that are just mentioned. In bold are the KOSs that consistently cover all research fields.

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Figure 3: Figure from Salatino et al. [16]. Analysis of KOSs according to their comprehensiveness, depth, frequency of update, and openness. Features of each KOS are evaluated using a color-coded system: green indicates a strong performance, orange signifies an acceptable performance, and red reflects poor performance. A feature is blank when the information is not available.

The following table summarises the code, Dockerhub, HF space repositories:

Repository	https://github.com/iNoBo/scinobo-fos-taxonomy
FoS Taxonomy Viewer V1	Markmap URL
FoS Taxonomy Viewer V2	Markmap URL
Paper(s)	[3], [4]

Table 3: Links to the repository and publications related to the Field of Science Taxonomy.

4.1.2. FoS Classifier

The FoS Classifier operates on the premise that publications predominantly cite other thematically similar works. It constructs a multilayer network (graph) where nodes represent venues (such as journals or conferences), and edges denote the citation relationships between them. The algorithm classifies a publication P into one or more FoS fields based on the venues of the publications that P references (out-citations) and those that cite P (in-citations). This allows the classifier to effectively classify publications using minimal metadata, relying only on journal or conference names and citation information (i.e. for Level 1(L1) - Level 4 (L4)). Recall from Section 4.1.1 that we have FoS fields for venues.

A snapshot of the multilayer graph of the FoS classifier is presented in Figure 4. In the Figure, the scientific publications (p_i), venues (v_i), and the FoS fields (f_i) are visible and are connected through different types of edges, like "cites" or "cited-by" for venues and scientific publications and "has field" or "subfield" for venues and FoS fields. The classification step consists of propagating information from the venues linked to FoS fields to scientific publications.

Figure 4: A snapshot of the multilayer graph of the FoS classifier.

There exist multiple ways to back-propagate information from the venue level to the publication level depending on the available metadata, as listed below:

- based on the published venue (namely *Published-by*)
- based on the referenced/cited venues (namely *References*)
- based on the referenced (cited) and citing venues (namely *References+Citations*)

For the readability and demonstration of this deliverable, we refrain from providing details for every way to propagate information from the venue level to the publication level. Please refer to the papers listed in Table 4 for further details. The FoS classifier by default utilises an ensemble of all the three aforementioned approaches with additional emphasis on the citations, to infer a publication to Levels 1 up to 4.

Each Level 5 FoS field is associated with a topic and several n-grams as Level 6 FoS fields, stemming from topic modelling as well. To that end, after inferring up to Level 4 and inherently filtering all the candidate Level 5 FoS fields, the inference at Level 5 will adhere to the same principles as those at higher levels, with a key difference: the FoS fields are propagated from the word level to the publication level, rather than from the venue level. We add the words that co-occur to the multilayer graph of the FoS classifier, drawing edges between them. The weights of these edges are their scores from their respective topic models. We also link the words with their corresponding Level 5 FoS fields in the graph¹⁴. Given a scientific publication, we retrieve its title and abstract. Since the topic modelling algorithm generates topics with words being from unigrams to trigrams, we generate all the unigrams, bigrams, and trigrams in the concatenation of the title and abstract. To classify a publication p , we must map those n-grams to the n-grams in the inference graph¹⁵. After the mapping, each candidate Level 5 FoS is ranked according to a weighting function¹⁶. The following Figure is provided as a reference point of the abovementioned process.

¹⁴ A complete snapshot of the multilayer graph in JSON format can be downloaded from <https://huggingface.co/datasets/iNoBo/scinobo-fos-inference-graph>.

¹⁵ For this mapping we also use semantic retrieval with the inference graph by utilising embeddings, which are numerical representations of words that capture semantic meaning. The embeddings for every n-gram in the FoS inference graph can be downloaded from <https://huggingface.co/datasets/iNoBo/scinobo-fos-graph-embeddings>.

¹⁶ Refer to the listed papers for more information.

Figure 5: FoS Classifier process. The green node represents a venue, the blue nodes represent FoS fields of all the levels apart from Level 5 and 6. The orange node is a Level 5 (note that it is represented with an ID); and is linked to a topic generated from topic modelling. The yellow nodes are n-grams under that topic.

Regarding the refinement and evaluation of the FoS classification algorithm after D3.1, the results of the classifier were used in practice by the pilots to construct and curate their scientific publication collections. This real-world usage provided an implicit validation of the classifier’s applicability across different pilot contexts. Moreover, the pilots are currently providing structured feedback on the FoS classification results through the BIP! Spaces platform.

Finally, we have experimented with both binary and scalar quantization techniques applied to the embeddings used in the FoS inference graph, following established approaches for embedding compression and approximate similarity search (hybrid and scalar quantization). While these experiments confirmed the feasibility of reducing the memory footprint of the model, no substantial improvements in inference speed were observed in the current deployment setting.

The following table summarises the code, Dockerhub, HF space repositories:

Code repo	https://github.com/iNoBo/scinobo-fos-classification
Docker hub	https://hub.docker.com/r/intelligenoborders/scinobo-fos-classification
Huggingface (HF) space	https://huggingface.co/spaces/iNoBo/scinobo-fos-classification
Paper(s)	[3], [4]

Table 4: Links to code, docker and demo repositories of the Field of Science Classifier.

4.1.3. FoS Taxonomy Mapper

The main objective of T3.1 “Scientific fields extraction from publications” is to provide the functionality required by the SciLake pilots and research communities in general, in order to identify scientific publications of interest. Building upon our FoS taxonomy (section 4.1.1) and FoS classifier (section 4.1.2) and D3.1 we developed the final version of the FoS taxonomy mapper tool.

The role of the FoS Taxonomy Mapper is to map external Fields of Science—originating from third-party taxonomies, ontologies, classification schemes, or user-provided keywords and phrases—to the most semantically relevant FoS labels of our taxonomy. Unlike earlier iterations of the tool, which relied on embeddings of full hierarchical taxonomy paths, the final approach adopts a flattened representation of the FoS taxonomy. Specifically, each FoS label from Level 1 up to Level 5 is treated as an independent semantic unit, leveraging the fact that Level 5 FoS entries are now explicitly named and no longer represented solely through keyword n-grams.

Each FoS entry is therefore represented as a simple structured object consisting of a single label and its corresponding level, for example:

```
{
  "fos_label": "Oncology & Carcinogenesis",
  "fos_level": "level_3"
}
```

or

```
{
```

```
"fos_label": "neural machine translation",  
"fos_level": "level_5"  
}
```

This design choice significantly improves interpretability and usability, as retrieved results directly correspond to human-readable FoS labels rather than composite hierarchical paths. It also enables more intuitive validation by users and domain experts, who can directly assess the semantic relevance of individual labels.

To perform semantic matching between external inputs and FoS labels, the mapper employs dense vector representations generated using the **nomic-ai/nomic-embed-text-v1.5**¹⁷ embedding model. This model provides high-quality, general-purpose text embeddings that are well suited for semantic similarity tasks in scientific and technical domains. Each FoS label (Levels 1–5) is embedded independently and indexed in a vector store (elasticsearch), enabling efficient similarity-based retrieval.

The tool supports three alternative retrieval strategies, which can be selected at query time:

- Cosine: Pure dense retrieval using cosine similarity between embeddings.
- Elastic: Lexical retrieval using BM25 over the FoS label text.
- Hybrid: A combination of dense and lexical retrieval, where results from both methods are merged and subsequently reranked.

For hybrid retrieval and result refinement, we employ the BAAI/bge-reranker-v2-m3 cross-encoder model, which reranks candidate FoS labels based on their semantic relevance to the query. While the tool supports all three approaches, empirical evaluation demonstrated that pure dense retrieval with cosine similarity consistently produced the most reliable results for FoS mapping. Lexical and hybrid approaches tended to overweight partial keyword matches, which is undesirable when the goal is to identify a coherent scientific field rather than a phrase-level overlap. For instance, for a query such as “brain tumor”, cosine-based dense retrieval correctly surfaces related fields such as “glioblastoma epilepsy”, whereas lexical or hybrid methods often prioritise labels containing individual tokens like “brain” or “tumor” irrespective of their conceptual relevance.

The number of retrieved FoS labels (k) is configurable and provided as an input parameter to the tool, allowing users to balance recall and precision depending on their use case.

The following table summarises the code, Dockerhub, HF space repositories:

¹⁷ <https://huggingface.co/nomic-ai/nomic-embed-text-v1.5>

Code repo	https://github.com/iNoBo/scinobo-taxonomy-mapper
Docker hub	https://hub.docker.com/repository/docker/intelligencenoborders/scinobo-taxonomy-mapper/general
Huggingface (HF) space	https://huggingface.co/spaces/iNoBo/scinobo-taxonomy-mapper
Paper(s)	-

Table 5: Links to code, docker and demo repositories of the Field of Science Taxonomy Mapper.

4.1.4. SDG Classifier

In recent years, the General Assembly of the United Nations has adopted a global indicator framework for their Agenda for Sustainable Development. To measure the relevance of scientific articles to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) of the UN, an SDG classifier, which classifies a given abstract of a scientific article to one or more SDG categories, has been developed. A silver corpus of SDG-related articles has been developed using a controlled SDG vocabulary¹⁸ to retrieve metadata of scientific articles found. The controlled vocabulary contains multiple combinations of keyphrases for each SDG category that enable the immediate categorization of an abstract upon their appearance. By using this controlled vocabulary along with an Elasticsearch installation containing scientific publications, we created a collection of abstracts. Then for each collection of abstracts we applied keyphrase extraction using Textacy's¹⁹ SGRank algorithm to extract additional keyphrases. A human curator reviewed the extracted keyphrases and augmented the controlled SDG vocabulary.

We utilised the above mentioned dataset to train two deep learning models based on a distilled version of BERT [5]. We used a pre-trained version of a distilled BERT model and further fine tuned a Multilayer Perceptron on top of the BERT model using the silver SDG corpus. During training we excluded data from underrepresented categories. We trained two models, one taking into account the vector representation of each token of the input through an attention mechanism and one model that takes into account the vector representation of the entire input sequence. As the deep learning models tend to be sensitive to key phrases found in the controlled vocabulary and several SDG categories are underrepresented in the corpus, a guided LDA [14] topic model was also trained using the key phrases found in the vocabulary. During training, a set of key phrases is assigned as a seed to each topic and the

¹⁸ <https://zenodo.org/record/4118028#.YvY4GHZBxPb>

¹⁹ <https://textacy.readthedocs.io/en/0.11.0/index.html>

topic is labelled with the corresponding SDG category. Guided LDA is thus given a fixed prior probability distribution of word occurrence for each topic. Then LDA is further tuned with the entire silver SDG corpus.

Overall, the classifier consists of two deep learning models and a guided LDA model, combined through a voting strategy to categorise an unseen article abstract. When processing an unseen scientific abstract, if a phrase from the controlled vocabulary is present, the abstract is assigned to the corresponding SDG category. The guided LDA then assigns a score to each topic and its related SDG categories, while the two deep learning models compute a probability distribution across the trained SDG categories. The abstract is ultimately categorised into its SDG classes when the computed scores surpass predefined, adjustable thresholds. In the following Figure, the pipeline of the SDG algorithm is presented:

Figure 6: Pipeline of the SDG algorithm.

Results from the SDG classifier were actively used by the pilots to curate their thematic collections of scientific publications. In parallel, an evaluation process is currently ongoing through the BIP! Spaces platform, where pilot users provide feedback on the relevance and adequacy of SDG assignments at the level of individual publications.

The following table summarises the code, Dockerhub, HF space repositories:

Code repo	https://github.com/iNoBo/scinobo-sdg-classification
Docker hub	https://hub.docker.com/repository/docker/intelligencenoborders/scinobo-sdg-classifier/general
Huggingface (HF) space	https://huggingface.co/spaces/iNoBo/scinobo-sdg-classification
Paper(s)	Classifying relevance for SDGs in Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe

Table 6: Links to code, docker and demo repositories of the SDG Classifier.

4.2. Citation-based impact analysis component

The citation-based impact analysis component is responsible for calculating indicators of scientific impact of research products by analysing the citation network into which they participate. The calculated indicators are, then, incorporated in the OpenAIRE Graph and, if useful, in some of the domain-specific SKGs.²⁰ The main use of these indicators is to provide ranking and filtering functionalities for the knowledge discovery service, helping researchers identify research products that are key for their investigations (see Section 4.4). In addition, some of the indicators are used to provide analytics for the trends related to particular scientific topics (see Section 4.3). The development activities of this particular component are related to tasks T3.2 “Multi-perspective analysis of scientific impact” and T3.3 “Impact propagation among research objects” of the SciLake project plan.

The following table summarises the code repositories and documentation websites that are related to this SciLake component.

Code repo(s)	Citation analysis library (BIP! Ranker): https://github.com/athenarc/Bip-Ranker
Publications	[9], [10], [11]

Table 7: Links to code repositories and documentation of the citation-based impact analysis component.

²⁰ The incorporation into the SKGs follows the [RA-SKG](#) extension of the [SKG-IF](#) standard, which dictates a particular representation for research-related indicators.

In the following paragraphs we provide more technical details related to the respective SciLake component.

Calculating indicators. The component supports the calculation of an array of citation-based indicators for research products (publications, datasets, software packages, etc.), each capturing a distinct aspect of scientific impact. Most of them can be applied to multiple types of research products, however, some of them are tailored and more appropriate for specific types.

The indicators calculated by the component, organised by the impact aspect they are capturing, are the following:

- **Influence indicators:** indicators of the "total" impact of each research product, i.e., how established it is in general.
 - *Citation Count (CC):* The total number of citations of the research product, one of the most well-known influence indicators.
 - *PageRank score (PageRank):* An influence indicator based on PageRank [7], a popular network analysis method. PageRank estimates the influence of each product based on its centrality in the whole citation network. It alleviates some issues of the Citation Count indicator (e.g., two products with the same number of citations can have significantly different PageRank scores if the aggregated influence of the products citing them is very different — the product receiving citations from more influential products will get a larger score).
 - *Indirect Citation count (ICC):* Indicator for non-publication contributions (mainly datasets and software). It is calculated as the total number of publication citations directly referencing the paper introducing a version of a research product.
 - *In-text mentions (IM):* Indicator for non-publication contributions (mainly datasets and software). Mentions of a research product within the body of a publication, without a formal citation (e.g., repository URL or DOI in footnote).
 - *Artefact Composite Impact Indicator (ACII):* An experimental impact indicator designed for non-publication contributions proposed by project partners. It combines different forms of citation evidence (direct, indirect, mentions) using a weighted aggregation approach (see also the paragraph on indicators tailored for non-publication products below).
 - *Field-Weighted Citation Impact (FWCI):* A field-weighted indicator that measures how a research product performs compared to the global average in its research field. An FWCI of 1.0 indicates that the product is cited exactly as expected for similar publications in the same field; values above 1.0 indicate

above-average impact, while values below 1.0 indicate below-average impact. In our analysis, the expected number of citations for each research product is computed by grouping them by concept, publication year, and product type and then averaging the citations within each group.

- *3-year FWCI (3y-FWCI)*: A time-restricted version of the FWCI that considers citations received within the first three years after publication. By limiting the citation window, this indicator captures the early relative impact of a research product, providing insight into how quickly it gains influence in its field.
- **Popularity indicators**: indicators of the "current" impact of each research product, i.e., how popular the product is currently.
 - *RAM score (RAM)*: A popularity indicator based on the RAM method [8]. It is essentially a Citation Count where recent citations are considered as more important. This type of "time awareness" alleviates problems of methods like PageRank, which are biased against recently published products (new products need time to receive a number of citations that can be indicative for their impact).
 - *AttRank score (AttRank)*: A popularity indicator based on the AttRank method [9]. AttRank alleviates PageRank's bias against recently published products by incorporating an attention-based mechanism, akin to a time-restricted version of preferential attachment, to explicitly capture a researcher's preference to examine products which received a lot of attention recently.
- **Impulse indicators**: indicators of the initial momentum that the research product received right after its publication.
 - *Incubation Citation Count (3y-CC)*: This impulse indicator is a time-restricted version of the Citation Count, where the time window length is fixed for all products and the time window depends on the publication date of the product, i.e., only citations 3 years after each product's publication are counted.

All indicators, except for the ICC, IM, and ACII, have been identified and experimentally tested in a series of previous works. More specifically, they have been tested by a large experimental study on ranking publications based on impact indicators [10], a subsequent study that offers improved indicators for the popularity case [9], and another study [11] that resulted in the creation of a dataset that also introduces the concept of impulse indicators. FWCI and 3y-FWCI are well-established, tested indicators that have been used by various scholarly data platforms (e.g., by Scopus' SciVal). ICC, IM, and several ACII variants have been qualitatively tested by pilot representatives within the project. More technical experiments, conducted without expert involvement, are currently ongoing and are intended to be reported in future

publications. Technical details related to these indicators can be found in later paragraphs of this section.

Moreover, it should be mentioned that all impact indicators are calculated on a *deduplicated citation network* to avoid counting multiple times citations made by multiple versions of the same product (a phenomenon that pollutes impact indicators calculated by traditional academic search engines, like Google Scholar). The nodes of the network are deduplicated using the most recent version of OpenAIRE's deduplication algorithm for research products²¹, hence each node in the network has a distinct OpenAIRE identifier. We also report the scores at PID level (i.e., we assign a score to each of the versions/instances of the product), however these PID-level scores are just the scores of the respective deduplicated nodes propagated accordingly (i.e., all versions of the same deduplicated product receive the same scores). During the previous process, we remove a small number of instances (having a PID) that are assigned (by error) to multiple deduplicated records in the OpenAIRE Graph.

In addition to the values of the indicators, we also offer an "impact class" for each product, which informs the user about the percentile into which the product score belongs compared to the impact scores of the other products in the database. These impact classes can be considered as (impact) indicators of categorical type (since they get values from a predefined set of literals) or "badges". The currently provided impact classes are:

- Class C1 (in top 0.01%)
- Class C2 (in top 0.1%)
- Class C3 (in top 1%)
- Class C4 (in top 10%)
- Class C5 (in bottom 90%)

When it is needed for these classes to be presented in a user interface (UI), for instance in the knowledge discovery portal described in Section 4.4, a combination of an icon and a colour code is used to provide an intuitive way for the end-users to overview the respective information. Moreover, we also provide topic-specific impact classes for the research products (these correspond to an additional set of categorical impact indicators/badges). In particular, based on a set of given associations between research products and topics, for each product and impact indicator, we calculate its class within the respective field (e.g., "in top 1% of the Cancer research field"). The calculation can be done on the basis of any set of product-to-topic associations. We have calculated such scores for the topics that correspond to L4/L5 fields produced by the Field extraction component (Section 4.1), however, after experimentation, we have selected to officially release the scores based on concepts provided

²¹ <https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/graph-production-workflow/deduplication/research-products/>

by OpenAlex. The main reason behind this decision was the coverage of the tested publication lists. For each product, we keep only the three most dominant concepts, based on their confidence scores, and only if the respective scores are greater than 0.3. Then, for each product and impact measure, we compute its class within its respective concepts.

Technical details on the work on indicators tailored for non-publication products. The assessment of scientific impact traditionally revolves around publications, but in today's research landscape, the impact extends beyond scholarly articles to encompass diverse research outcomes like software and datasets. Although the impact indicators presented in the previous paragraph are calculated for all types of research products, not just publications, the respective scores may not fully capture the impact characteristics of other types of research products, such as datasets and software, which we will refer to as “*research artefacts*” from this point forward. The primary reason is that the impact of an artefact is often indicated not only by direct citations but also by other types of mentions. Acknowledging the use of an artefact can be done in various ways, and there is no universally adopted set of best practices across all domains and researchers.

Different *forms* of citations and mentions of research artefacts should be considered differently when trying to assess their potential impact or significance. For instance:

- *Direct citations from publications:* Citations of a research artefact within the reference list of a publication indicate that the artefact has been directly acknowledged and possibly used in the cited work.
- *Direct citations from other research artefacts:* Citations of a research artefact within the content of another research artefact, such as formal reference in the metadata of a dataset or software package.
- *Indirect citations:* Citations directly referencing the paper introducing a research artefact.
- *In-text mentions in publications:* Mentions of a research artefact within the body of a publication, without a formal citation.
- *Mentions in the textual descriptions of other artefacts:* References to a research artefact within the descriptions or documentation of other artefacts, such as software documentation mentioning the use of a specific dataset.

Adapting these multiple forms of citations could help provide a more comprehensive view of the impact of research artefacts, especially when it comes to in-text mentions, as it is a common occurrence for references to artefacts such as datasets and software to be relegated to e.g., footnotes.

In addition to the *form* of the citation, other features can be considered for citation indicators to capture a more nuanced understanding of the impact and influence of research artefacts. In particular, taking into account whether an in-text mention of a given artefact signifies that it is being reused or introduced, for instance; or whether an indirect citation corresponds to a contextual, generic mention of the paper introducing the artefact, or whether it mentions it because it is reused or compared to in the citing work.

The above can be taken into account by leveraging two SciLake components developed in the context of the Smart Reproducibility Assistance service: the research artefact analysis and citation-context assisted replication assessment tools (see D4.2). The former finds in-text mentions of research artefacts and classifies them as “ownership” or “reuse”, while the latter analyses citations to determine the intent of a given citation from one work to another (e.g., generic, comparison, reuse) in addition to the semantics (e.g., an introduced research artefact is being referred to in particular) and the polarity of the mention, which provides additional information about the reception of the cited work.

A series of artefact-specific indicators can be then obtained: number of direct (formal) citations; number of indirect citations, and their specific features regarding reuse; number of in-text mentions, and their specific features regarding reuse; in addition to more straightforward indicators such as number of views and downloads. Furthermore, by weighting these different dimensions in terms of relevance for impact—e.g., reuse signifying a more direct impact than comparison, which in turn is more impactful than a contextual mention—one can also define composite indicators. In this case, we consider two possible methodologies:

- *Direct composite indicators:* In this case the research objects are considered independently, assigning different weights to various types of citations or mentions based on their origin or use. As described in D4.1, this approach is similar in nature to the u-Index²², which attempts to distinguish between “awareness” and “usage” citations to research artefacts using the section of the citing work in which the mentions appear as a proxy to make the distinction. Here, instead, we attempt to go beyond by directly considering the context and nature of citations to quantify the impact of research artefacts.
- *Network metrics:* Alternatively, network metrics can be applied to this task, with the different types of relationships between research artefacts materialised as different weighing schemes to be applied to the edges of the citation network. In this approach, the entire structure of relationships within the network is taken into account,

²² <https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201843>

highlighting the interconnectedness and influence propagation across different artefacts. In this case, the existing network metrics already implemented for traditional publications could be leveraged.

4.3. Topic analysis component

This component provides domain experts with powerful functionalities for monitoring trends in scientific topics. Specifically, it captures and visualises the evolution of topics over time, offering valuable insights. This allows experts to better understand a field of interest, identify emerging areas, and predict which topics are likely to gain attention in the near future. Such capabilities can be useful for researchers and other stakeholders (e.g., officers in funding organisations) for informed decision-making and strategic planning. Furthermore, they provide useful insights for the knowledge discovery process.

The component is based on SciTo [13], a topic monitoring tool that has been developed in the past by ATHENA RC. SciTo relies on a database of mappings between scientific publications and research topics. The contents of this database can be populated by a well-established scholarly data source or using a topic modelling approach on the scientific texts (e.g., titles, abstracts and/or full texts of scientific publications). SciTo's initial version leveraged the results of the execution of the LDA (Latent Dirichlet Allocation) algorithm [14] on the titles and abstracts of a set of scientific publications (more details in the respective publication). In the context of SciLake, we have experimented with using concepts from OpenAlex and low-level FoS fields from the FoS Taxonomy being developed by SciNoBo (see also Section 4.1.1). The production release of the relevant features of the Knowledge discovery portal (Section 4.4) is based on the OpenAlex concepts for reasons related to the coverage of the tested publication lists and the existence of standardised confidence scores for the connections between the topics and the publications.

The main functionality of SciTo is that it offers intuitive visualisations on how scientific topics evolve in the course of time. These visualisations exploit the number of publications related to the topics of interest, their impact in the respective scientific domain, and other information, such as the similarity between different topics (when this is applicable). In the context of the SciLake project, SciTo functionalities are being adapted, extended and integrated into the Knowledge discovery portal (Section 4.4, also known as the "BIP! Spaces" platform), where more details regarding the visualisations can be found. This integration created a powerful knowledge discovery tool for domain experts, incorporating all relevant developed features. An important extension of SciTo's visualisation functionalities implemented within SciLake was the addition of a Sankey diagram that illustrates the evolution of the top topics related to a

query of interest, in terms of the total number of relevant publications over time (see Section 4.4 for details and screenshots).

The following table summarises the code repositories and documentation websites that are related to this SciLake component.

Code repo(s)	https://github.com/athenarc/bip-services
Publications	[13]

Table 8: Links to code repositories and documentation of the topic analysis component.

4.4. Knowledge discovery portal

The key objective of this component is to assist researchers and domain experts in the knowledge discovery process. For that reason, it was essential for SciLake to build a user interface (UI) to integrate the previously mentioned components and offer relevant functionalities in this direction. In this section we describe this UI which essentially is a knowledge discovery portal, called “BIP! Spaces”.

The following table summarises the code repositories and documentation websites that are related to this SciLake component.

Code repo(s)	https://github.com/athenarc/bip-services
Documentation	https://github.com/athenarc/bip-services/blob/main/README.md
User guide	https://bip.imsi.athenarc.gr/site/help#bip-spaces
Publications:	[15]

Table 9: Links to code repositories and documentation of the knowledge discovery portal component.

Basic search functionalities. BIP! Spaces is a customizable academic search engine designed so that it can be tailored to meet the specific needs of specific organisations or communities (e.g., the SciLake pilots). Its core functionality includes offering a keyword-based search for research products, such as publications, datasets, software, and other types of research objects. This search can be applied on textual descriptors of these objects (e.g., publication abstracts). More importantly, each space is connected with an SKG that encodes annotations related to the domain of interest determined by the organisation or community that owns it.

The search results can be presented in various ways, such as filtered or organised based on impact indicators, to facilitate the identification of the most valuable items and help prioritise the resources that could be more valuable for a particular investigation of interest. Beyond providing convenient ways to retrieve result lists, the tool also offers various summarization options, including automatically generated summaries of the top articles' findings and intuitive visualisations. These features enhance the knowledge discovery process and uncover important findings, trends or latent relationships between domain-specific entities based on the relevant literature. Figure 7 demonstrates a screenshot of the respective UI.

Figure 7: A snapshot of the BIP! Spaces user interface displaying domain-specific annotations coming from an SKG.

In the figure, annotations from the SKG connected to the respective space are displayed inside the search results. In this example (that comes from the space of the cancer research pilot), three types of annotations are provided for the second search result: diseases (35 in

total) related to the respective article, drugs (5), and tissues (22). By default, all annotations of each type are hidden and can be revealed by clicking the button that corresponds to the annotation type. In the example shown, the annotations related to drugs and tissues for the second result have been expanded, while those related to diseases remain hidden. If desired, users can also reveal all annotations on the page at once by clicking the “Expand all annotations” button located at the top of the search results list.

When the annotations of a type are visible, the users can reveal more details about each of them by clicking its rounded box. This action renders a pop-up window that includes the relevant information (see also Figure 8).

Figure 8: Details for a particular annotation in BIP! Spaces UI.

Moreover, the end-users are able to open a detailed page for each annotation, where all research products related to it are listed together with general information about the annotation (see Figure 9). On the top of the page, all information related to the corresponding entity (in our example, a drug named “cytidine”) is displayed (this information comes from the SKG of the space). Then, a couple of visualisations, which summarise the number of research products per year that relate to the respective annotation and the citations they have received, are shown. Finally, the list of all related research projects appears; the end-users can select the criterion used for the ordering of the items in the list from a relevant drop-down menu item.

Drug: Cytidine

Class: Pyrimidine nucleosides

Name: Cytidine

Groups: Experimental

Kingdom: Organic compounds

Id: DB02097

Superclass: Nucleosides, nucleotides, and analogues

Synonyms: Cytidine|ZINC000002583632|46507502|17562|6175|CTN|C00475|CHEMBL95606|EXPT01051|5940|D07769

Provided by: Scilake Cancer Research Graph

Annotation Evolution

Ordering: Popularity

3,363 results (169 pages)

Summarize top results

[Cancer nanomedicine: progress, challenges and opportunities](#) Found 3 versions

Jinjun Shi; Philip W. Kantoff; Richard Wooster; Omid C. Farokhzad
 Nature Reviews Cancer - 2016

Nanotechnology | Engineering ethics

Open Access | Publication | Copy Link

[Silver Nanoparticles: Synthesis, Characterization, Properties, Applications, and Therapeutic Approaches](#) Found 3 versions

Xi-Feng Zhang; Zhi-Guo Liu; Wei Shen; Sangiliyandi Gurunathan
 International Journal of Molecular Sciences - 2016

Nanotechnology

Open Access | Publication | Copy Link

Figure 9: An example annotation details page.

In addition, it is worth mentioning that the system offers its end-users the option to filter out search results based on the annotations. More specifically, they can select to keep only results that are connected to at least one annotation of a particular type (see the “Show results with” filter at left side of Figure 7). Apart from that, there are a couple of other related filters that allow the end-users to remove from the results list any entry that is not connected to any annotation from the SKG or to keep only results that are connected to particular annotation values.

Finally, it should be noted that the annotations mechanism is also responsible for displaying information related to reproducibility (e.g., the values of particular reproducibility-related indicators - see Deliverable D4.2²³ for more details).

Usage of impact indicators. It's important to highlight how the impact indicators, calculated by the citation-based impact analysis component (Section 4.2), are utilised by the UI. The end-user can choose how search results are ranked using the "Ordering" dropdown menu item located below the main keyword search box. Different ranking criteria can be selected to suit various use cases. For example, ranking by "Influence" or "Citation count" brings fundamental publications to the top, while ranking by "Popularity" highlights more recent results that are currently having a significant impact²⁴. Additionally, the end-user can easily assess the impact class (for details see Section 4.2) of each search result by examining the set of impact icons displayed in the top right corner of each result. Moreover, the relative impact class for each topic associated with the result can be viewed using similar icons within the rounded box of each topic. Figure 10 illustrates these UI elements.

Figure 10: Impact indicators in the BIP! Spaces UI.

The implementation of these functionalities in BIP! Spaces relies on three main indexes. A Solr²⁵ index supports keyword search, a MariaDB relational database stores domain-independent information from the OpenAIRE Graph, and a graph database instance enables graph queries (using Cypher) on the domain-specific SKG. Communication with the

²³ doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18339329

²⁴ More insights for these criteria and their semantics can be found in Section 4.2.

²⁵ Apache Solr: <https://solr.apache.org/>

SKG is facilitated through the open Lake API provided by the SciLake ecosystem (see also Deliverable 2.1).

Customization. Regarding customization capabilities, BIP! Spaces can be tailored to cater to the unique requirements of different scientific fields, ensuring researchers have access to the most relevant and useful tools for their specific areas of study. Specifically, the tool allows the creation of focused "spaces," which are instances of the underlying search engine customised for a particular domain.

Customization options extend beyond basic appearance adjustments, such as using a specific logo, colour scheme, and tagline for the space (just to name a couple indicative options). The entire search experience can be personalised by defining custom pre-selected filters or default ranking methods for search results. However, the most significant customization feature is the ability to configure each space to connect with an SKG of interest and consume its contents to offer tailored services to the end-users. For instance, this integration allows information for domain-specific entities (and their connections to research products) that is included in the SKG to be offered as annotations of the search results (as it was elaborated in the previous paragraphs), enriching the search experience.

Furthermore, the SKG contents can further enhance the search experience by providing functionalities like query expansion: synonyms of entity names from the nodes of the SKG can be suggested to the end-user during keyword searches, improving the effectiveness and accuracy of the searching mechanism (see Figure 11). The owner of the space can determine which synonyms from the SKG will be used for the query expansion functionality.

The screenshot shows the Sci!lake search interface. At the top, there is a search bar containing the text 'thorax'. Below the search bar, there is an 'Ordering:' dropdown menu set to 'Influence'. To the right of the search bar, there is a red 'Expansion suggestion' button. Below this, a red-bordered box highlights a message: 'Looking for a Tissue? You can broaden your search by including related terms and identifiers such as: *thorax, chest* Expand search'. Below the message, there are 'Key topics' with filters for 'Cancer research (111)', 'Pathology (61)', 'Immunology (25)', 'Internal medicine (19)', and 'Oncology (18)'. The search results show '111 results (6 pages)' and a pagination control with page numbers 1 through 5. There is also a 'Summarize top results' button and an 'Expand all annotations' button. The main result shown is a publication titled 'Efficient delivery of small interfering RNA to bone-metastatic tumors by using atelocollagen in vivo' by Yusuke Yamamoto et al., published in 'Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences' in 2005. The result includes a 'Cancer research' topic tag and various utility buttons like 'Open Access', 'Publication', 'Search Context', and 'Copy Link'.

Figure 11: Expansion suggestion based on synonyms.

All customisation options are performed through the administration UI that is responsible for creating and maintaining the respective spaces. This advanced level of customization ensures that BIP! Spaces can adapt to the evolving needs of various scientific domains, organisations, and communities, offering a highly specialised and efficient research tool.

Topic & annotation evolution visualisations. The most important topics related to each publication are displayed in the search results, along with a confidence score (when applicable for the classifier used). This score indicates the relevance of the topic to the publication, providing end-users with a clear understanding of the connection's significance. In the UI, this score is represented by a circle, with the coloured portion corresponding to the respective score, ranging from 0 to 1. Furthermore, a summary of the most important topics related to the publications from the end-user's query is displayed at the top of the results, along with the number of related results. The end-user can click on each topic's rounded box to view graphs showing the number of publications related to that topic per year, as well as the corresponding citations. The following figure illustrates a snapshot of the respective user interface.

Figure 12: A snapshot of the BIP! Spaces user interface displaying topics.

Additionally, the end-users can compare how the key topics related to their query have evolved over the past few years by clicking the visualization button located to the right of the key topics. When clicked, a pop-up window opens displaying two ribbon charts²⁶ that visualize the relative ranking of each topic per year (see Figure 13), based on the number of relevant publications (at the top of the figure) or the citations received (at the bottom), respectively .

²⁶ In earlier versions of this functionality, we have experimented with Sankey diagrams (see D3.1), however, the ribbon chart was identified as more appropriate for our use case.

Topic Evolution (Last 10 Years)

Figure 13: Visualisation of key topics evolution for an example query.

AI-generated summaries. Registered BIP! Space end-users also have the option to ask for AI-generated summaries of the top search results. This can be done by clicking on the “Summarise top results” button placed at the top right corner of the search results section. The summaries are generated by a generative AI model that synthesizes the titles and abstracts from the top-k search results (more details on the model used can be found in our relevant publication [17]). By default, k is set to 5, but users can adjust this value to regenerate the summary based on a different number of results. Figure 14 demonstrates an example of the respective functionality.

The screenshot shows a search interface with a search bar containing 'sequencing diagnosis'. Below the search bar, there is an 'Ordering:' dropdown menu set to 'Influence'. A 'Key topics' section displays several categories: Cancer research (7,359), Oncology (2,482), Internal medicine (1,932), Genetics (1,565), and Pathology (1,258). A navigation bar shows '7,359 results (368 pages)' and a pagination control with buttons for '1', '2', '3', '4', and '5'. A 'Summarize top results' button is visible on the right. Below the navigation bar, a summary box is shown with the text: 'Use top 5 results. Summarize' and a 'Copy to clipboard' button. The summary text reads: 'Cancer genomics reveals that tumorigenesis involves the accumulation of somatic mutations, but the patterns and clinical implications of these genetic alterations vary significantly across cancer types. Early sequencing efforts established that common solid tumors like breast and colorectal cancers exhibit a genomic landscape dominated by a few frequently mutated "mountains" amid many low-frequency "hills" [1]. Subsequent deep sequencing of individual cancers has illuminated the complex clonal evolution within tumors, showing that primary breast cancers can harbor significant mutational heterogeneity, with only a subset of somatic mutations present in a metastatic lesion being detectable in the primary tumor years earlier, indicating substantial evolution with progression [3]. This spectrum of genomic evolution is particularly wide in primary triple-negative breast cancers (TNBCs), which range from having few mutations to hundreds, with only a fraction expressed and with varying clonal frequencies that challenge the notion of universal founder mutations for genes like TP53 [4]. In contrast, certain hematologic malignancies are defined by highly specific, clonal driver mutations, such as the BCR-ABL fusion mRNA in chronic myeloid and acute lymphocytic leukemias, which serves as a sensitive diagnostic marker independent of cytogenetic findings [2]. Similarly, a single, ubiquitous oncogenic mutation, BRAF V600E, was identified in all patients with hairy-cell leukemia, implicating constitutive MAPK pathway activation as a central pathogenic event and a potential therapeutic target [5]. Collectively, these studies underscore that understanding cancer biology and advancing diagnosis and therapy require delineating both the common mutated pathways and the specific clonal genotypes of individual tumors [4, 5, 1].'

Figure 14: Example of AI-generated summary of top 5 search results for the query “sequencing diagnosis”.

This feature offers an interesting use case: comparing summaries generated using different ranking schemes. For example, a substantial difference in the narrative between summaries based on popularity versus influence ranking could indicate a shift in the prevailing literature's focus over time.

Service feedback. BIP! Space owners can enable the “Feedback Mode” to gather end-user input. This mode adds two distinct feedback mechanisms to the space:

- Result Evaluation: Users can assess the relevance or appropriateness of search results by clicking the “✓” (tick) or “x” (cross) icon next to an entry.

- Annotation Verification: Users confirm the correctness of an annotation by clicking “✓” or report an error by clicking “x”.

Figure 15 demonstrates the respective functionality.

Figure 15: Service feedback functionalities.

All feedback (“✓” or “x”) is immediately stored in the internal database upon clicking. Crucially, this feedback does not immediately alter the underlying database or knowledge base. Changes based on the collected feedback can be implemented later, upon request from the Space owner. If a feedback button was clicked accidentally, the user can click the same button again to cancel the submission.

SciLake pilot representatives have access to these functionalities, allowing them to provide feedback as they experiment with the portal’s features. This feedback offers useful insights into the contents of the SKGs and the quality of the outputs produced by various SciLake components (like those described in earlier sections of this report). This mechanism has been used to support some of the project’s evaluation activities, which will be reported in Deliverable D5.2, to be submitted by March 2026.

5. Conclusion

In this report, we described the final release of the smart knowledge discovery service that the SciLake project has developed. This service is built on top of the Scientific Lake that the project is delivering and leverages the contents of the underlying SciLake's Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs). The service is using the SKGs to calculate indicators of scientific impact for research products and offer, based on them, useful functionalities to researchers so that they could prioritise their reading of the relevant literature when searching for a specific subject of interest, uncover latent knowledge that could be instrumental in accelerating their research conclusions, and identify emerging trends related to research topics of interest.

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